

The background of the cover is a composite image. On the left, there is an aerial photograph of a river winding through a dry, brown landscape. On the right, there is a dark blue background with a white line graph showing fluctuating data points, overlaid with a faint grid pattern.

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**INNOVATIVE
APPROACHES TO
WATER RESOURCE
MANAGEMENT IN
ARID REGIONS IN THE
CONTEXT OF
CLIMATE CHANGE**

PROCEEDINGS
(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

WICAR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO
WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT
IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT
OF CLIMATE CHANGE**

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

INTERNATIONAL PROGRAM COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Umarov A.A. First Vice-Rector for Academic Affairs, UWED

Vice Chairman

Dadabaev T. Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. Professor, Head of Department, UWED

Rasulov A. S. Professor, UWED

Seytov A.J. Professor, UWED.

Program Committee Members:

Rasulov A. S. Professor, UWED

Seytov A.J. Professor, UWED.

Dalabaev U. Professor, UWED

Umarova Sh. Dotsent, UWED

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Djalalov M.M. Vice-Rector for Digital Transformation and Economy, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. Head of the Department of System Analysis and Mathematical Modelling, UWED

Seytov A.J. Professor, UWED.

Organizing Committee Members:

Abdullaev E.E. (Dean, UWED, Uzbekistan)

Dalabaev U. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova M. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Umarova Sh. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

CONFERENCE SECRETARIAT

Umarova Sh.G. (Head of the Secretariat), Buriev A., Kasimova N.J., Maraimova K. Sh., Khasanova D.R., Yarashev I., Solaeva M., Mustafakulova A. Kh., Akabirkhodjaeva D.R.

International Scientific and Practical Conference -2026

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference innovative approaches to water resource management in arid regions in the context of climate change on May 19, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The conference aims to discuss key issues of effective water resource management in arid regions under climate change, develop and apply innovative approaches and mathematical and computational modeling methods, share recent research results and practical experience, and strengthen international academic cooperation in this field.

Key Themes of the Conference:

1. Water Diplomacy and Integrated Approaches in International Relation: Interdisciplinary Approaches to Sustainable Development, Communication and Global Security

- Issues of systemic analysis in international relations and world politics in the context of water diplomacy
- Economic, environmental and energy aspects of sustainable development
- Systemic approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. Mathematical and computer modeling of optimal water resources management under climate change

- Optimal water resource management under climate change
- Modeling water resource dynamics and climate variability
- Methods of applied and computational mathematics in irrigation system modeling.

3. Environmental and Hydrogeological Processes in the Aral Sea Region: Analysis Based on Modern Technologies

- Analysis of hydrogeological processes in the Aral Sea region
- Application of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data technologies to environmental challenges
- Simulation and stochastic modeling of environmental and hydrogeological processes in the Aral region.

The event was conducted in a hybrid format with participation in English, Russian, and Uzbek. The conference provided a high-level platform for scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Numerical modeling and optimization of water flow management in main irrigation canals based on the finite difference method

Nietbay Uteuliev^{1, a}, Gafur Djaykov^{1, b}, Sherzod Yadgarov^{1, c}

¹ Nukus State Technical University, Nukus, Uzbekistan

a) utewlievn@mail.ru

b) gafur_djaykov@mail.ru

c) Corresponding author: shyadgarov@mail.ru

Abstract. The article examines the task of optimal water resource management in a main irrigation canal. To describe the dynamics of water flow change, a differential transfer model is used, accounting for the flow distribution along the canal and the distributed water intake. As an optimal criterion, a functional is introduced that includes the deviation of the actual water flow from the required optimal value along the entire length of the canal and in the outlet section. To numerically solve the problem, the finite difference method is applied, based on which a stable difference scheme and an iterative algorithm for calculating water flow in a spatiotemporal grid are constructed. Particular attention is paid to the relationship between the control action at the channel input and the value of the target functional. It has been shown that optimizing the control signal allows for the stabilization of water flow distribution along the canal and increases the efficiency of water resource utilization. The proposed numerical approach can be used in modeling and automated management of irrigation systems.

Keywords: optimal management, irrigation canal, water resources, finite difference method, difference scheme, functionality, numerical modeling.

INTRODUCTION

In the management of modern hydraulic engineering and water management systems, it must be taken into account that the dynamics of water flow in main canals are complex in nature. Simplifying complex mathematical models and finding their optimal solutions for the precise and rapid control of such processes is one of the urgent tasks. This section provides a detailed analysis of optimal control methods for simplified models describing the unstable movement of water resources in the main canals of irrigation systems. In particular, the finite difference method was used to convert continuous processes into discrete form and to effectively organize computational work. [1-3].

The algorithm for numerically solving the problem based on the finite difference method and its relationship with the functional is presented step-by-step. The algorithm for numerically solving the problem of optimal water resource management in the main canal of the irrigation system using the finite difference method and its relationship with the target functional is presented:

1) To optimize the change in water discharge along the main canal over time and distance, the following objective functional is adopted:

$$I(u) = \int_0^T \int_0^l (Q(x,t) - Q^*)^2 dx dt + \int_0^T (Q(l,t) - Q^*)^2 dt \rightarrow \min, \quad (i)$$

where $Q(x,t)$ is the time-dependent water flow along the channel, Q^* is the required optimal flow, and $u(t)$ is the control action at the head of the channel.

The purpose of this functional is the optimal management of water resource consumption along the channel and $Q(x,t)$ in the downstream pool according to Q^* [4-6].

Functional minimization is carried out when the following dynamic constraint conditions are met:

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = q(x, t), \quad Q(0, t) = u(t), \quad Q(x, 0) = Q_0(x), \quad (\text{ii})$$

where $v > 0$ is the wave propagation velocity, and $q(x, t)$ is the water withdrawal value distributed along the channel.

2) To numerically calculate the differential equation, a discrete grid is introduced for the variables x and t .

By channel:

$$x_i = i\Delta x, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N_x, \quad \Delta x = \frac{l}{N_x}.$$

By time:

$$t^n = n\Delta t, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N_t, \quad \Delta t = \frac{T}{N_t}.$$

The grid variable is defined as follows:

$$Q_i^n \approx Q(x_i, t^n)$$

thus, it is possible to calculate the value of Q at each point along the channel and at each time step [7-8].

3) Since $v > 0$ in the model, the main direction of wave propagation moves forward along x . Therefore, a finite difference scheme is chosen to give a stable and physically meaningful result in numerical calculation:

$$\frac{Q_i^{n+1} - Q_i^n}{\Delta t} + v \frac{Q_i^n - Q_{i-1}^n}{\Delta x} = q_i^n.$$

From this equation, the following iterative calculation formula follows:

$$Q_i^{n+1} = Q_i^n - \frac{v\Delta t}{\Delta x} (Q_i^n - Q_{i-1}^n) + \Delta t q_i^n.$$

This formula allows you to calculate channel-wide consumption at each time step based on previous time values. [9-10].

4) Boundary and initial conditions:

$$Q_i^0 = Q_0(x_i),$$

$$Q_0^n = u(t^n).$$

The most important point here is that the flow rate at the main point of the channel is completely determined by the control signal.

5) To ensure the stable operation of the finite difference scheme and the absence of oscillations during the calculation process, the stability condition must be met:

$$\frac{v\Delta t}{\Delta x} \leq 1.$$

In practice, this condition is an important criterion for the correct selection of calculation steps.

6) The functional integral I is reduced to the form of a discrete sum for numerical calculation:

$$I \approx \sum_{n=0}^{N_t-1} \sum_{i=0}^{N_x} (Q_i^n - Q^*)^2 \Delta x \Delta t + \sum_{n=0}^{N_t-1} (Q_{N_x}^n - Q^*)^2 \Delta t,$$

where the first addend takes into account the total quadratic deviation along the channel and the second addend takes into account the quadratic deviation at the output point (i.e. $x=1$) [11].

Thus, the functional yields the following two main conclusions:

- functionally fully dependent on the grid-calculated (Q^n);
- (Q_i^n) is formed entirely through $u(t)$ control.

7) The relationship between the control effect and functionality is represented by the following chain:

$$u(t) \Rightarrow Q_0^n \Rightarrow Q_i^n \Rightarrow I(u),$$

that is:

- $u(t) \rightarrow$ input flow rate;
- input flow \rightarrow changes the dynamics of the $Q(x,t)$ throughout the entire channel;
- $Q(x,t) \rightarrow$ determines the value of the functional $I(u)$

Therefore, stabilization of flow along the channel is achieved by optimizing the $u(t)$ [12-13].

8) The numerical solution algorithm for the problem is implemented in the following stages.:

Step 1. Add input parameters:

$$l, T, v, Q^*;$$

Step 2. Network construction:

$$x_i, t^n, \Delta x, \Delta t;$$

Step 3. Provision of an initial condition:

$$Q_i^0 = Q_0(x_i);$$

Step 4. Assign initial value for control:

$$u^0(t^n);$$

Step 5. For each time step:

- boundary condition:

$$Q_0^n = u(t^n);$$

- calculation using a finite difference scheme:

$$Q_i^{n+1} = Q_i^n - \frac{v\Delta t}{\Delta x}(Q_i^n - Q_{i-1}^n) + \Delta t q_i^n;$$

Step 6. Calculating the functional based on the calculated Q_i^n :

$$I = \int_0^T \int_0^l [Q(x,t) - Q^*]^2 dx dt + \int_0^T [Q(l,t) - Q^*]^2 dt \rightarrow \min;$$

Step 7. Update management:

- Gradient projection method or
- by random search method

$$u^{m+1}(t) = (u^m(t)).$$

9) The general cycle of finite-difference optimization—the numerical solution of optimal control—is implemented as an iterative process:

$$u^m(t) \Rightarrow Q^m(x,t) \Rightarrow I(u^m) \Rightarrow u^{m+1}(t),$$

where in each iteration, the control $u(t)$ is updated and the functional value decreases.

Thus, in the finite difference method, the partial differential equation is discretized in the grid and Q_i^{n+1} is calculated at each time step. Since the initial boundary condition is $Q_0^n = u(t^n)$, the dynamics of $Q(x,t)$ depend entirely on the control signal. Therefore, the functional $I(u)$ is directly linked to control through the Q_i^n calculated in the grid and minimized by optimization algorithms.

Figure 1. Change in water flow rate using the gradient projection method.

In the section of canal parameters, the result obtained using the gradient projection method is shown in Figure 1, with values at $L = 25$ km, $T = 24$ hours, $Q^* = 60$ m³, $H = 2.3$ m, and $Max = 300$. In this case, the initial distance, i.e., the turbulent movement of water in the upper reaches of the section, is reduced, and the water flow for 14 kilometers is equalized with the optimal flow, i.e., the water withdrawal value of each water consumer, and optimal management is achieved.

Figure 2. Changes in water consumption using the random search method.

In the section of canal parameters, the result obtained using the random search method is shown in Fig. 2, with values at $L=25$ km, $T=24$ hours, $Q^*=60$ m³, $H=2.3$ m, and $Max=300$. In this case, the initial distance, i.e., the turbulent movement of water in the upper reaches of the section, is reduced, and the water flow at 14 km is equalized with the optimal flow, i.e., the water withdrawal value of each water consumer, and non-uniform control is observed.

CONCLUSION

The article examined the issue of optimal water resource management within the main irrigation canal. To characterize the dynamics of water discharge changes, a differential displacement model was used, taking into account the distribution of flow along the canal and distributed water intake. A functional was introduced as an optimality criterion, including the deviation of the actual water flow in the entire length of the canal and the outlet section from the required optimal value. The finite difference method was used for the numerical solution of the problem, on the basis of which a stable difference scheme and an iterative algorithm for calculating water flow in a time-space network were constructed. The relationship between the control action at the channel inlet and the target functional value was considered. The optimization of the control signal made it possible to stabilize the distribution of water flow along the canal and increase the efficiency of water resource utilization.

REFERENCES

1. Seytov, A., Abdurakhmanov, O., Kakhkhorov, A., Karimov, D., Abduraimov, D. Modeling of two-dimensional unsteady water of movement in open channels. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 2024, 486, 01023.
2. Turaev, R., Seytov, A., Kuldashaeva, S., Nortojev, U. Algorithms for calculating limits in water management in irrigation systems. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 2023, 401, 02016.
3. Aybek Seytov; Lyudmila Varlamova; Azam Khudayberdiev; Niyetbay Uteuliev; Sherzod Yadgarov; Dauletyar Seytimbetov. Usage of finite element method for modeling twodimensional unsteady water movement in open channels. *AIP Conf. Proc.* 3147, 030034 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0210332>.
4. Aybek Seytov; Azimjon Khusanov; Azam Khudayberdiev; Niyetbay Uteuliev; Sherzod Yadgarov; Dauletyar Seytimbetov. Development of algorithms for modelling water management processes on main canals. *AIP Conf. Proc.* 3147, 030032 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0210329>.
5. Aybek Seytov; Azimjon Khusanov; Azam Khudayberdiev; Niyetbay Uteuliev; Sherzod Yadgarov; Dauletyar Seytimbetov; Otabek Ergashev; Olim Abduraxmanov. Development of algorithms for solving problems of optimisation of water resource management in irrigation systems. *AIP Conf. Proc.* 3147, 030033 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0210330>.
6. Aybek Seytov; Lyudmila Varlamova; Sayfiddin Bahromov; Yusup Qutlimuratov; Bakhadir Begilov; Seytimbetov Dauletyar. Optimal management of water resources of large main canals with cascades of pumping stations. *AIP Conf. Proc.* 3147, 030022 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0210523>.
7. Uteuliev, N.U., Qutlimuratov, Y.Q., Yadgarov, S.A. Using the methods and optimizing criteria in making the managing decisions of agricultural production. *International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies: Applications, Trends and Opportunities, ICISCT 2019, 2019*, 9011907.
8. Ermol'ev, Yu.M., Mikhalevich, M.V., Uteuliev, N.U. Economic modeling of international water use (the case of the aral sea basin). *Cybernetics and Systems Analysis*, 1994, 30(4), pp 523–527.
9. Nurmukhamedov, T.R., Gulyamov, J.N., Tashmetov, T.Sh. Development of the Information System for Inventory Control of Wagon Depot Stock. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 2022, 2432, 060026
10. Seytov, S.J., Eshmatova, D.B. Discrete Dynamical Systems of Lotka–Volterra and Their Applications on the Modeling of the Biogen Cycle in Ecosystem. *Lobachevskii Journal of Mathematics*, 2023, 44(4), – P. 1471–1485
11. Varlamova Lyudmila, P., Seytov Aybek, J., Bahromov Sayfiddin, A., Shokhjakhon Sh, B., Mirzaolimov Akhmadjon, K. *Digital Agricultural Ecosystem: Revolutionary Advancements in Agriculture*, 2024, pp 339–368.
12. Butkovsky A. G. *Theory of optimal control of systems with distributed parameters.* - 1965.
13. Klimov V.E. Optimal operating mode of pumping stations equipped with axial pumps. *Hydraulics and Land Reclamation*, 1970, No. II. PP. 30-35.